

**INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN IMPROVING
NATIONAL HUMAN CAPITAL**

Gaibnazarova Zumrat Talatovna

DSc, Professor of the department «Fundamental economics» Tashkent state university of
economics

e-mail: z.gaibnazarova@tsue.uz

mob. phone: +998 99 444 11 77

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Abstract. *The article deals with the strategic objectives of quality education, the creation of public and professional accreditation, the decision of new forms of social partnership, the rule of law and the types of contracts that would assist universities in the preparation of the formation of labor demanded by the market and specialists with professional competence, as well as enterprises, to provide their staffing needs.*

Keywords: *human capital, education, innovation, integration, production, labor market, quality assurance, academic mobility, accreditation.*

The most important problem in building a competitive economy is the quality of the human resource - the spiritual, moral, educational, and professional level of citizens, since in today's world the competitive advantage is not provided by the size of the country, but by the level of natural resources and the power of human capital.

The development of the education system is one of the priority areas of state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Priority is reflected in improving the quality and content of education and, accordingly, curricula, stimulating the work of teachers [1].

The sphere of higher education in Uzbekistan today is characterized by the modernization of the reform process and the further implementation of the National Training Program. At the same time, the accumulated experience is analyzed and generalized, the development of the labor market and specific socio-economic conditions are taken into account. The necessary legal, personnel, scientific, methodological, material, technical and financial conditions have been created to ensure the reform of the higher education system. Structural reform and modernization of the content of higher education continues [2].

Today, we can state with certainty the fact that higher education is, above all, a tool for social inquiry. The main focus of today's youth is to determine their life status, therefore, the social function of modern higher education prevails in the minds of young people.

The current state policy defines and ensures the organizational content and ideology in the creation and development of the economy, within which the education system occupies a special place in the chain of the relationship «education - science - production». To select the best solutions to the problems of integration of education, science and production, it is necessary to take into account traditions, evaluate the existing mechanisms of integration and the results achieved.

The training of competent personnel for industries of the economy, primarily depends on the quality of educational processes, taking into account the requirements of the labor market. This is primarily determined by the conformity of the requirements of the vocational education system to the needs of employers.

At present, the initial state is the issue of attracting public and professional organizations to the process of formation and implementation of educational activities, which ensure the necessary level of quality of education. Based on this, independent forms of assessing the quality of education, and mechanisms for identifying, supporting and disseminating the best examples of innovative educational activities should be developed.

The strategic objective of ensuring the quality of education, in our opinion, is achieved by solving cardinal measures in the following areas:

- the implementation of an independent public and professional assessment of the activities of educational programs of higher education institutions, with the aim of developing a modern system of innovative education, taking into account factors, including information and methodological support of licensing, certification and state accreditation of educational programs;

- the development of new forms and mechanisms for assessing and monitoring the quality of the activities of higher education institutions in implementing educational programs to ensure the objectivity, reliability and transparency of procedures for evaluating the activities of educational institutions;

- improving the mechanisms for recognizing the equivalence of documents on education to increase the academic mobility of students and teachers, development of cooperation in the field of educational services, which will contribute to the integration of the educational system of Uzbekistan in the global educational space;

- increasing the competitiveness of vocational education, the direct involvement of leading specialists in the industry of the economy in training personnel and leading universities that have passed the examination of educational programs, through public-professional accreditation, as well as universities that have experience in training personnel according to the new generation educational standards, which were developed with the participation of employers , public and professional associations;

- the creation of mechanisms focused not only on the domestic socio-economic needs of the country, but also on ensuring the competitiveness of Uzbekistan in the global labor market;

- the creation of a system of social and professional accreditation of specialist training, which allows to identify those higher education institutions in which the quality of training in a particular field is at the proper level and meets the requirements of the labor market.

Public accreditation allows you to:

- assistance, improvement and development in Uzbekistan of education and activities in all their manifestations related to educational, scientific and technological areas;

- improving the quality of the educational process, counseling, research, development of innovative solutions, technology transfer;

- the provision of a wide range of educational services, ensuring relations with the public, industry, science;

- creating conditions for the most effective realization of the creative potential of society in the interests of developing scientific and technological progress and innovative development;

- the development of international relations and contacts in the field of innovative education;

- promoting the integration of scientists, teachers of higher educational institutions and specialists with higher education in the international scientific and educational space;

- improving the educational system in the ranking of countries competitive in the international market for educational services.

The procedures for social and professional accreditation should be simplified and unified as a whole in all areas of education, naturally taking into account the specifics of each area, and oriented to the labor market and should be adjusted taking into account professional training, based on the fundamental and universal nature of education, personality development and the formation of social responsibility . The educational system should focus on the labor market ahead of the system of labor market requirements and be at the modern level of development of science, engineering and technology [4].

Acceleration of scientific and technological progress, implementation of reforms is impossible without qualified personnel with deep and solid knowledge in the chosen specialty, information from related fields of science, the ability to independently improve the knowledge gained, organizational skills and creative initiative, own the skills of research work, etc. Higher school is called upon to form these qualities [5].

The main objective of the higher education system is currently improving the quality of education. The traditional understanding of the quality of education includes the level of training of graduates who are capable of effective professional activity, to quickly adapt in various conditions, who know how to use the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in practice, and are also capable of self-education throughout life.

The scale and depth of the upcoming scientific and technological transformations make us especially concerned about the quality of training. It is necessary to carry out structural adjustment on the basis of scientific and technological progress, as this question is posed today, we must seriously raise the status of personnel with higher education. A comprehensive solution to the problem of education is needed by improving the quality of education, differentiating the training system. Education should be combined with the solution of practical problems, with the needs of social development. It should be ahead of him, constantly improving. The search for such paths, the identification of possible options for further movement in this area are now very important. This is directly related to the search for fundamentally new ideas, guided by which you can move forward in the development of an innovative economy.

Improving the system of higher education is determined by three components: creativity; education technology concepts; financial, economic and legal components on the basis of which an education system is being created [6]. At the same time, it helps to prepare a specialist who is ready for change and risk, generating ideas, for effective work in the field of production and other areas of socio-economic life.

Training involves the use of the following methodological components:

- goals;
 - principles;
 - content of education;
 - methods;
- forms and means of training.

The methodological component in the training of personnel, in addition to the goal, are general didactic principles:

- scientific;
- motivation;

- systematic;
- continuity and consistency;
- The connection of theory with practice;
- consciousness and activity, etc.

Moreover, each of them specifically manifests itself in higher education. This primarily refers to the principle of science, since all that is new in science and technology affects educational technologies. Specific principles are:

- dynamism-vision of modern and new trends and prospects for the development of science and technology;
- systematic - allowing you to holistically represent the educational system;
- integrity-reflection in the content and process of training for professional activities;
- integration and differentiation of the process of training specialists from production;
- professional orientation-orientation of the content of education, methods and forms of training to the ultimate goal of specialist training;
- continuity is a reflection of the current education content.

The main consumers of graduates of higher educational institutions are enterprises, organizations and institutions of various nature and subordination expecting graduates of relevant competence.

Higher vocational education is an open system where universities and employers are links in one chain. Employers must formulate requirements for both the quantity and quality of training of professional personnel, and universities to meet these requirements.

Currently, on the part of employers, there is an insufficient level of graduates.

At the same time, the main complaint against universities is the isolation of graduates from practice, the inability to work with modern and innovative high-tech equipment. The way out of the situation is to deepen the content of production practices, attracting specialists from enterprises to conduct classes, and adapting disciplines to real life. At the same time, employers believe that in order to improve the quality of training, the organization of practice in specific conditions is necessary.

In general, the problem of high-quality training of specialists is due to the high efficiency of interaction between the university and employers. In this regard, the participation of employers in the training of professional personnel is a condition for the preparation of competent graduates who meet the requirements of employers.

The solution to this problem involves new forms of social partnership, legal norms and types of agreements that would assist universities in the training of specialists, and enterprises in providing for their staffing needs.

Among the most common areas of joint activity of representatives of universities and employers are:

- practical training of students in advanced enterprises;
- expanding the range of educational services of universities in demand on the labor market;
- development and review of educational and program documentation;
- conducting by employers' representatives of training sessions, master classes;
- participation of employers in the final state certification of graduates;
- internship of teachers at enterprises;

- participation of employers in scientific and practical conferences, training projects, scientific seminars, etc.;
- project integration (joint research, the creation of joint small centers, etc.);
- employment of graduates.

The interaction of universities and employers in the process of students undergoing various practices, which are an integral part of educational programs. It is practice that ensures students gain professional work experience and, thus, acts as the «leading factor for the effective formation of a high level of professional competence of future specialists».

Accordingly, the programs of practices provided for by relevant state standards should focus on the continuous improvement of the professional level of students' development, first of all, through the integration of their theoretical and professional-practical, educational and research activities [3]. However, experience shows that the level of organization of practices is not enough today for students to gain real work experience and productive mastery of their professional and practical skills, production skills and advanced labor methods. The reason for this state of affairs is the weak ties between universities and employers.

Universities and employers should be interested in creating a system that unites their efforts to form students' professional competencies. However, employers, although they are ready to combine efforts with universities to optimize the components of educational programs related to practices, expect proposals on specific forms of interaction from the higher education institutions themselves. This circumstance sharply increases the role of graduate departments, organizing and teaching guidance for a particular type of practice in areas (specialties), in the implementation of the socio-economic partnership of universities with employers. It is they who become the catalyst for social and economic dialogue with external consumers of the university's educational services and ensure the formation and strengthening of partnerships with them.

In order to increase the effectiveness of interaction with employers, it is advisable for university graduating departments to develop cooperation programs and conclude relevant agreements.

The main tasks facing universities and employers in the formation of personnel with professional competencies demanded by the labor market include:

- combination of competencies and content of practice; determination of compliance of given competencies with types of professional activity;
- compiling a list of professional competencies to be acquired or developed by students in the process of practice;
- coordination of a set of conditions for the effective formation of professional competencies of students;
- feedback from employers on the level of formation of professional competencies with the aim of subsequent adjustments and improvement of EP, improving the effectiveness of training programs in the university as a whole;
- the search for new forms of production practices that ensure that students gain significant practical experience and contribute to their guaranteed employment in the specialty (for example, by alternating with theoretical classes throughout the academic year; registration of trainees to work with payment for their work; order for term and diploma studies projects, etc.);

- stimulating students' creative activity and research activities, creating professional test cases and self-testing for them for students to successfully master self-promotion technologies and build their own careers, etc.

In our opinion, partnerships between universities and employers are an effective means of improving the quality of higher professional education, creating additional conditions for the formation of included EP competencies, expanding and deepening the practical knowledge of students, however, they can give the greatest benefit for partnership entities when integration processes join the cooperation processes .

It can be stated that the effectiveness of interaction between universities and employers in the interest of improving the quality of training of professional personnel increases significantly if universities succeed in transferring their strategic partners-employers from the position of outside observers and passive consumers of educational services to the position of interested participants in educational and innovative processes that contribute to mastering students with a set of professional competencies that meet the requirements of modern labor market.

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